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ANTIOXIDANT, ANTI-INFLAMMATORY PROPERTIES AND OX-LDL UPTAKE PREVENTION POTENTIAL OF *PHYSALIS MINIMA* AT TWO STAGES OF MATURITY

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ABSTRACT

The fruits of *Physalis minima*, an underexploited food plant, are known to be antioxidant in nature and suitable for consumption in both unripe and ripe stages. Hence it is important to find out the antioxidant activity of the fruit in both ripe and unripe stage to determine which stage of fruit could be exploited for nutraceutical and pharmaceutical research. Free radicals initiate many diseases including atherosclerosis, cancer etc. It was found that the unripe fruit methanol extract had higher free radical scavenging activity compared to that of ripe fruits as measured by DPPH, nitric oxide scavenging assay, phosphomolybdate assay and LDL oxidation inhibition assay. Further the unripe fruits were shown to have higher foam cell preventing activity than ripe fruits as seen by their abilities to prevent ox-LDL uptake by RAW 264.7 macrophages which indicates their potential to counteract atherosclerotic plaque formation. Nitrite radicals initiate and accelerate the process of atherosclerotic plaque formation by creating an inflammatory environment. The efficiency of unripe fruits to scavenge nitrite radicals in lipopolysaccharide stimulated RAW 264.7 macrophages was very high compared to that of ripe fruits indicating their anti-inflammatory potential. The methanol extract of unripe fruits had higher total phenolic content (6µg gallic acid equivalent/mg dry weight) which reduced to 3.92µg gallic acid equivalent/mg dry weight upon ripening. HPLC profiling indicated an excess of cinnamic and chlorogenic acid in unripe fruits compared to ripe fruits and disappearance of sinapic acid and ferulic acid from ripe fruits.

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INTRODUCTION

Physalis minima plants (commonly called 'wild cape gooseberry') bear fruits which are used to make desserts and jams in Hawaiian islands. They are also used in pie fillings.^[1] The fruits were shown to have anti-lipid peroxidative activity in goat liver in vitro.^[2] The plant was shown to have anticancer activities in lung and breast cancer cell lines^[3], anti-inflammatory and analgesic activity in mice models^[4], hypoglycemic activity in mice models^[5] and is known to be a good appetizer with a very sweet taste. Furthermore, they are rich in vitamin C and therefore, have good prospects of making people use them to a greater extent. The fruits have also been used as an ingredient in medicinal oil, which have been traditionally used for the treatment of spleen disorders (like spleen enlargement) in India.^[6] The fruits are also considered as tonic, diuretic and purgative in many countries.^[6]

Oxidative stress causes extensive damage to intracellular and extracellular proteins, lipids and nucleic acids (DNA and RNA). It plays an important role in the development of tissue damage, inflammation leading to development of various diseases.^[7] Free radicals play a key role in these reactions and have been found to be the main cause of oxidative stress.^[7] Even though reactive nitrogen species (RNS) and reactive oxygen species (ROS) are important to carry normal biological process^[8], overproduction of these species such as hydroxyl radical (*OH), and nitric oxide (NO*), could lead to chronic inflammation and may contribute to diseases such as diabetes, cancer and atherosclerosis.^[9]

Since Atherosclerosis is an inflammatory disease, it is important to find plants with anti-inflammatory properties. Natural antioxidants and lipid lowering interventions such as food supplements, spices, and herbs find extensive application in prevention of atherosclerosis because of their ability to prevent in vitro antioxidant capacity and plaque formation.^[10]

Previously, it has been shown by Villa-Rodríguez et al.^[11], that the antioxidant activities of fruits and vegetables depend on ripeness stage of fruits, cultivar and agronomic conditions and that there is a change in phytochemical accumulation during different stages of maturity.

Thus the objective of the present study is to find out the changes in phytochemical profile and antioxidant properties between unripe fruit and ripe fruits to determine the best stage of consumption.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

MATERIALS:

All chemicals were purchased from Sisco Research Laboratories, India except for Hydrogen peroxide which was purchased from RFCL (RANKEM), India, potassium dihydrogen phosphate and Fetal bovine serum from Himedia laboratories, India, Butyl Hydroxyl Anisole (BHA), DPPH, dialysis membrane, Dulbecco's modified eagle media (DMEM), antibiotics (Streptomycin-Penicillin), Thiobarbituric acid, aluminium chloride, 1,1,3,3-tetramethoxypropane, paraformaldehyde, 1, 1'-dioctadecyl-3,3',3',3'-tetramethylindocarbocyanine perchlorate (DiI, Sigma-Aldrich Pvt. Ltd) and Folin-Ciocalteu's reagent from Sigma-Aldrich Private Limited, India.

METHODS:

Plant collection and extraction:

Physalis minima plants were collected from watery areas of the Mysore district, Karnataka State, India, and grown outside in a greenhouse. The fruits were collected in month of October, and dried at 55°C in oven reduced to fine powder by milling. The resulting powder was subjected to extraction with 80% Methanol. The methanol extract was concentrated using a rotary evaporator and dissolved in the appropriate solvent for the antioxidant assays, and, for the tissue culture, the extract was dissolved in dimethyl sulphoxide (DMSO), diluted further with DMEM complete medium (supplemented with 10% fetal calf serum (FCS), and 1% penicillin/streptomycin) (Gibco), and filter sterilized.

Bioactivity assays:

DPPH radical scavenging Assay:

2,2-diphenyl-1-picrylhydrazyl (DPPH) was used for determination of free radical scavenging activity of the extracts according to Brand-Williams et al.^[12] Different concentrations of each of the extracts/standard was added to 4 ml methanol solution of DPPH. The reaction mixtures were incubated for 30 min at room temperature in dark. After 30 min, absorbance was read at 517 nm (Shimadzu UV 160 Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan). The inhibition ratio was calculated using the formula:

$$\text{DPPH radical scavenging (\%)} = 100 \times (A_0 - A_S) / A_0, \dots\dots\dots (1)$$

where A_0 = control absorbance, A_S = sample absorbance.

Results were expressed as IC_{50} calculated as the concentration required to produce 50% inhibition.

Nitric oxide scavenging activity:

Nitric oxide scavenging activity was measured spectrophotometrically according to the protocol of Lee^[13]. Sodium nitroprusside (5 mM) in phosphate buffer saline (0.1M, pH 7.4), was mixed with different concentrations of extract/standards, dissolved in methanol, and incubated for 30min at 25°C. After 30 min, an aliquot of 1.5ml of the reaction mixture was mixed with 1.5ml of Griess' reagent. The intensity of the pink colour formed during the process of diazotization of the nitrite radicals with sulphanilamide followed by coupling with naphthylethelene diamine was measured at 546 nm (Shimadzu UV 160 Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan) along with a control, which contained all the reagents except the extracts. The nitrite radical scavenging activity was calculated using equation (1). Results were expressed as IC_{50} calculated as the concentration required to produce 50% inhibition.

Total Antioxidant capacity:

Evaluation of total antioxidant capacity of the extracts was done using phosphomolybdenum method described by Prieto et al. [14] 3ml reagent solution (6M sulphuric acid, 28mM sodium phosphate and 4mM ammonium molybdate) and 0.3 ml of extract solution (1mg/ml) were mixed. The incubation of reaction mixture was done for 90 min at 95°C. Absorbance of the solution was measured against blank at 695 nm using a spectrophotometer (Shimadzu UV 160 Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan). Antioxidant capacity of the extract was expressed as equivalents butyl hydroxyanisole (μg BHA /mg extract).

Low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation inhibition assay:

The efficacy of extracts in preventing the LDL oxidation was evaluated by the method described by Orrego et.al [15]. The LDL (100 μg protein/ml in phosphate buffered saline (PBS), pH 7.5) was incubated with two different concentrations (50 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) of the extracts or ascorbic acid for 30 min in 50 mM PBS (pH 7.5), and the volume made upto 4 ml. The positive control contained neither extracts, nor BHA, but only LDL. The reaction was started with the addition of 10 μM copper sulphate (CuSO_4) to all tubes. After 20h of incubation, the reaction mixture (0.5ml) was added to 0.25ml of trichloroacetic acid (2.5%, v/v) and 0.25ml 2-thiobarbituric acid (1% w/v), vortexed and kept in a boiling water bath for 30min. After cooling to room temperature, the pink chromogen developed was extracted into n-butanol (2.0 ml) and read at 532 nm (Shimadzu UV 160 Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan). Results were expressed as percentage inhibition calculated using equation 1.

Cell Culture:

The murine macrophage RAW 264.7 (1.0×10^6 cells/ml) cells were purchased from the NCCS, Pune and cultured in Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Media (DMEM) supplemented with 10% heat-inactivated fetal bovine serum, streptomycin (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{mL}$), and penicillin (100 U/ml) at 37°C in a 5% CO_2 atmosphere.

Lipopolysaccharide (LPS) stimulated nitrite scavenging assay:

RAW 264.7 cells were grown in 96-well plates (2×10^5 cells/well) using Dulbecco's Modified Eagle Media (DMEM) and treated with different concentrations (30 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ and 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$) of *P. minima* ripe and unripe extract for 1 h. [16] Nitric oxide (NO) production in the cells was induced by the addition of 1 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ of LPS followed by incubation for 24 hours. Subsequently, 100 μl of the supernatant media was added to 100 μL of Griess' reagent and incubated for 15 min. The absorbances were recorded at 540 nm using an ELISA plate reader (Benchmark, Bio-Rad Laboratories, CA, USA). Results were expressed percentage inhibition which was calculated using equation 1.

Foam cell formation:

Prevention of foam cell formation was assessed by measuring DiI-labeled oxLDL internalization. RAW 264.7 cells (1×10^5 cells/well on coverslips) were incubated with 100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ DiI-oxLDL in the presence/absence of extracts/ for 48 hours at 37 °C in 5% CO_2 . After 48 hours, internalization of DiI was assessed in a fluorescence plate reader using excitation wavelength of 540 nm and emission wavelength of 565 nm. Results were expressed percentage inhibition which was calculated using equation 1. [17]

Phytochemical analysis:**Total flavonoid content:**

The total flavonoid content in the extracts was determined by using the colorimetric assay originally described by Basniwal et al. [18] with slight modifications. Briefly, 0.3 ml solution of extracts (1 mg/ml) in 45% ethanol was separately mixed with 8 ml of 10% aluminium chloride (w/v) in distilled water and 4 ml 0.2 M sodium acetate (CH_3COONa). The mixed solution was then immediately diluted to a volume of 25 ml with deionised water, mixed thoroughly and left at room temperature for 30 min. The absorbance of the reaction mixture was measured spectrophotometrically at 350 nm (UV-2450 Spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan). Total flavonoid content was calculated from a standard curve using Quercetin (Sigma-Aldrich). The results are expressed as μg quercetin equivalents / mg extract.

Total phenolic content:

Total soluble phenolics of the extracts were determined by the method of Gulcin et al. [19] with Folin-Ciocalteu reagent using gallic acid as the standard. For each extract, 1 ml aliquot (1 mg/ml) was added to test tubes and the final volume adjusted to 10 ml by the addition of distilled water. Folin-Ciocalteu reagent (1 ml) was added to this mixture, followed by 3 ml 2% (w/v) sodium bicarbonate (NaHCO_3) 3 minutes later. Subsequently, the mixture was shaken for 2 h at room temperature and the absorbance measured spectrophotometrically at 760 nm (Shimadzu UV 160 spectrophotometer, Shimadzu, Japan). The concentration of total phenolic compounds in the extracts was determined as μg gallic acid equivalents/mg extract by using a standard gallic acid graph.

High performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) analysis of Total Phenolic Content:

The phenolic compounds were analysed by HPLC analysis using a Shimadzu chromatograph (LC 20-AS HPLC), equipped with dual pump, UV detector (SPD 20A) and an YMC-Pack ODS-AQ column (12 nm, 5 μm , 150 x 4.6 mm) as described by Vivian et al. [20] The separation and elution was done by using a binary gradient mode. The mobile phase consisted of acetic acid in filtered Milli-Q water adjusted to pH 2.6 as solvent A and 20% of solvent A in 80% acetonitrile as solvent B. The injection volume of the sample was 20 μl with a flow rate of 1.2ml/min and run time of 60 min. The solvent system was run as follows (% solvent A/solvent B): 0 min (10/90), 40 min (50/50), and 45 min (10/90). The resolution of phenolics was detected at 280 nm.

Statistical analysis:

All experiments were performed in sets of threes (n=3) (three trials in individual experiments) and results were expressed as mean \pm SD. Statistical analysis was carried out with (SPSS package version 10.0, SPSS, Inc., Chicago, IL) using ANOVA followed by Tukey's test ($p < 0.05$). Correlation analysis was performed using Microsoft excel software 2007.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Antioxidant and anti-inflammatory activities of *P. minima* fruits at ripe and unripe stages:

Free radicals cause oxidation of LDL which in turn cause the macrophages to take up ox-LDL in an unregulated fashion to cause foam cell formation.^[21] Hence the abilities of *Physalis minima* ripe and unripe fruits to scavenge free radicals and hence their antioxidant activities were tested and compared by different assays like DPPH radical scavenging activity, phosphomolybdate assay and nitrite radical scavenging activity. Their potential to protect against plaque formation in atherosclerosis was tested by their ox-LDL induced foam cell preventing and nitrite radical scavenging abilities in lipopolysaccharide stimulated RAW 264.7 macrophages.

DPPH contains a free proton radical whose absorption decreases in the presence of scavengers of proton radical. The reduction in the colour is in accordance with the hydrogen donating power of the extracts.^[22] The results showed that unripe *Physalis* fruit methanol extract had the highest antioxidant activity with an IC_{50} of 300 μ g/ml compared to ripe fruits (Table 1). Another method of evaluating the antioxidant activity of the extracts was phosphomolybdate assay. In the phosphomolybdenum method, molybdenum VI reduced to molybdenum V to form a green phosphate complex. The total antioxidant activities (TAA) of Methanol extracts of ripe and unripe fruits of *P. minima* are shown in Table 1. The TAA of unripe fruits was very high (141.33 μ g BHA equivalent/mg dry wt) when compared to ripe fruits which was around 48.33 μ g BHA equivalent/mg dry wt. Methanol extract of the unripe has higher TAA than corresponding ripe fruits which indicate the correlation between TAA and free radical scavenging activity. Previously, *P. minima* stem and leaves methanol extracts showed 63.01% and 68.78% inhibition ability at 200 μ g/ml conc. in DPPH radical scavenging activity.^[23]

Excessive Nitrite radical production plays an important role in the progression of atherosclerosis and many other inflammatory diseases like cancer and neurodegenerative diseases by the production of peroxynitrite radicals which are highly oxidative.^{[24] [25]} Nitrite radical (NO) plays a major role in manifestation of atherosclerosis. Nitrite radical is implicated in diabetes, inflammation, cancer and other pathological conditions.^[26] Hence it is important to identify the plants extracts which have capacity to counteract the effect of Nitrite radical formation and prevent the adverse effects of excessive Nitrite radical generation in human body. The Nitrite radical was more effectively scavenged by unripe fruit methanol extract than that by ripe fruits of *P. minima* (Table 1). The results showed that unripe *Physalis* fruit methanol extract had the highest antioxidant activity with an IC_{50} of 24 μ g/ml which was almost equal to that of the standard antioxidant, BHA (25 μ g/ml) (low IC_{50} indicates high activity). Previously, it was reported that *P. minima* leaf ethanol extract showed an IC_{50} of 46.63 μ g/ml in nitrite radical scavenging assay.^[27] This activity was found to be lower than that obtained for unripe fruits (lower IC_{50} indicates higher activity).

Table-1: Antioxidant activities and phytochemical analysis (flavonoid and phenolic content estimation) of methanol extracts of unripe and ripe *P. minima* fruits.

Extracts	DPPH radical scavenging activity (IC_{50} μ g/ml)	Nitric oxide radical scavenging activity (IC_{50} μ g/ml)	Total antioxidant activity (μ g BHA equivalents/mg dw)	Total flavonoid content (μ g QE/mg dw)	Total phenolic content (μ g GAE/mg dw)
Unripe	300 ^a	24 ^a	141.33 ^a	58.45 ^a	6.00 ^a
Ripe	350 ^b	40 ^b	48.33 ^b	58.00 ^a	3.92 ^b
BHA	10 ^c	30 ^a	-	-	-

Values have been expressed as mean \pm SD (standard deviation) from triplicate measurements (n=3) from three trials. Values in each column succeeded by different letters differ significantly from each other by Tukey's test after ANOVA ($P \leq 0.05$). QE- Quercetin Equivalent, GAE-Gallic Acid Equivalent, BHA- Butyl hydroxyl anisole, dw- dry weight of extract

Inhibition of LDL oxidation and macrophage ox-LDL uptake by *P. minima* fruits at ripe and unripe stages:

Inhibition of Low density lipoprotein (LDL) oxidation:

Native LDL does not contribute to vascular dysfunction leading to atherosclerosis. Reactive oxygen species (ROS) degrade LDL to conjugated dienes and further oxidation leads to the formation of aldehydes including malondialdehyde (MDA). The oxidized LDL is processed by a scavenger receptor of macrophages, leading to cholesterol ester accumulation. These lipid-laden macrophages become foam cells which, in time, create fatty streaks in blood vessel walls and later block the arteries by the formation of atherosclerotic plaques which are major causative factors of heart attacks. In addition, oxidized LDL has many other atherogenic effects in vascular subendothelium.^[17] Inhibition of human LDL oxidation by plant extracts and standard (BHA) (calculated using equation 1) are given in the Table 2. The result showed that at 5 hrs, the methanol extract of unripe fruits could efficiently inhibit LDL oxidation at a 100 μ g/ml which is as efficient as that of standard (BHA). The ripe fruits also could inhibit LDL oxidation. However, its activity was lower than that of unripe fruits and BHA. These results are in agreement with previous studies on another species of *Physalis*- *Physalis peruviana* where the LDL oxidation inhibition ability of the fruits decreased with increase in maturity.^[28]

Table-2: Prevention of LDL oxidation by two different concentrations (50 µg/ml and 100 µg/ml) of *P.minima* fruit extracts are compared to that of BHA at two different time points (5h and 20h) under oxidizing conditions.

Extract	Conc. (µg/ml)	Percent Inhibition (5 hrs)	Percent inhibition (20 hrs)
Control	-	-	-
Unripe Methanol	50	31.37 ^a	29.23 ^a
Unripe Methanol	100	92.16 ^c	86.54 ^c
Ripe Methanol	50	25.00 ^b	17.00 ^d
Ripe Methanol	100	37.50 ^f	27.00 ^{ab}
BHA	50	92.16 ^c	69.23 ^e
BHA	100	94.12 ^c	78.85 ^f

Control represents LDL under oxidizing conditions mentioned in text without extracts/standard. Values have been expressed as mean \pm SD (standard deviation) from triplicate measurements (n=3) from three trials. Values in each column and across different rows succeeded by different letters differ significantly from each other by Tukey's test after ANOVA ($P \leq 0.05$). Results were expressed as percentage inhibition.

Oxidation of LDL results in an unregulated uptake of ox-LDL molecules by the macrophages which lead to the formation of lipid filled foam cells which form the building blocks of atherosclerotic plaques in arteries. [21] Atherosclerotic plaques eventually increase in size and reduce the blood supply to the heart. [21] In the present study, it was seen that unripe *Physalis* fruit methanol extract had the highest inhibition effect on ox-LDL uptake and thus prevention of foam cell formation. Percentage inhibition of ox-LDL uptake (as indicated by the uptake of fluorescently labeled ox-LDL) shown by extracts were calculated as shown in equation 1. There was a dose dependent increase in the inhibition of ox-LDL uptake in case of both unripe and ripe fruits (Fig.1). However, unripe fruit methanol extracts showed a higher amount of inhibition of ox-LDL compared to those of ripe fruits.

Fig-1: Effect of methanolic extracts of unripe and ripe *P.minima* fruits on ox-LDL uptake by measurement of intracellular concentration of fluorescently labeled ox-LDL and results are expressed as percentage inhibition.

Effect of methanolic extracts of Ripe and unripe fruits on Nitric oxide (NO) production in RAW 264.7 macrophages: another inflammatory parameter

The main trigger for the development of atherosclerotic plaque is inflammation in the arterial area. [29] Bacterial lipopolysaccharide (LPS)-treated macrophages are used as inflammatory models since they mimic the inflammatory effects caused by cytokines. [30] To estimate the scavenging potential of extracts on NO production in RAW 264.7 cells the cells were incubated with different concentrations of unripe and ripe fruit methanol extract ranging from 5-200µg/ml for 1 h after which the cells were stimulated with LPS (1 µg/ml) for 24 h more. The supernatant was collected and estimated for NO release by Griess' reagent. Unstimulated macrophages produced undetectable levels of nitrite, but treatment with LPS induced a release of NO to the culture medium. Percentage inhibition of NO formation shown by extracts were calculated as shown in equation 1. Pretreatment with methanolic extracts from unripe and ripe could inhibit the formation of nitrite radicals. However, the unripe fruits could significantly inhibit the formation of nitrite when compared to ripe fruits. The results showed that unripe *Physalis* fruit methanol extract showed the highest anti-inflammatory activity starting from a dose of 30µg/ml (Fig. 2). At this concentration unripe fruit methanol extract showed a percentage inhibition of 80% whereas the ripe fruit methanol extract showed a percentage inhibition of only 40%.

Fig-2: Effect of methanolic extracts of unripe and ripe *P. minima* fruits on LPS-induced nitric oxide in RAW 264.7 macrophage cells.

Phytochemical analysis:

Since most of the activity has been previously linked to the presence of polyphenols in fruits and vegetable, the total phenolic content and total flavonoid content was estimated in both ripe and unripe fruits. The results indicated that of the total phenolic content and total flavonoid content estimated, total phenolic content of unripe fruits were significantly higher than that of ripe fruits (Table 1). Thus a decline in some phenolic compounds could have led to a decrease in the activity of ripe fruits. Similar results were obtained previously in citrus fruits, where the antioxidant activity and phenolic content of unripe fruits were higher than those of the ripe fruits.^[31]

In order to examine the phenolic compounds whose concentrations had changed during the ripening processes, HPLC analysis (Fig.3 and Table 3) of phenolic compounds was performed in the case of unripe and ripe fruits. It was found that unripe fruits had a high concentration of cinnamic acid and chlorogenic acid compared to ripe fruits. Ferulic acid and sinapic acid were found to disappear from the fruits upon ripening. This is the first report on the HPLC analysis of phenolic composition in *P. minima* fruits to the best of the authors' knowledge.

Fig-3: HPLC chromatogram of phenolic compounds in *P. minima* ripe and unripe fruits.

Table-3: HPLC profiling of phenolic compounds in *P. minima* ripe and unripe fruits at 280nm.

Peak no.	Phenolics	Unripe ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{g FW}$)	Ripe ($\mu\text{g}/100\text{g FW}$)
1	Gallic acid	ND	1115.86
2	Protocatechin	1417.6	1648.91
3	Chlorogenic acid	2223.25	136.96
4	Vanillin	407.65	1404.59
5	Coumaric acid	256.22	4455.29
6	Sinapic acid	1271.5	ND-
7	Ferulic acid	1753.34	ND
8	Cinnamic acid	545.64	297.69

FW-fresh weight

ND-not detected

Correlation analysis of these 4 phenolic components with LDL oxidation inhibition assay and total antioxidant activity by phosphomolybdate assay showed a Pearson correlation coefficient $r=1$ (Table 4) indicating a very high contribution of these compounds in the antioxidant activity of the fruits. Ferulic acid is known to be anti-cancerous, anti-diabetic and anti-atherosclerotic in nature.^[32]

Sinapic acid has been shown to prevent oxidative stress, reduce hypertension and protect against myocardial dysfunction.^[33] Chlorogenic acid has been shown to have antioxidant, hypolipidemic and hypoglycaemic activity^[34] Cinnamic acid has been shown to protect against cardiovascular diseases.^[35]

The other phenolic components gallic acid, coumaric acid, protocatechin and vanillin show negative correlation with these assays (Table 4). Thus phenolic compounds like cinnamic acid, chlorogenic acid, sinapic acid and ferulic acid could be responsible for the antioxidant and ox-LDL uptake inhibition activity of the fruit.

Table-4: Correlation coefficients between total phenolic content, concentrations of individual phenolic compounds (separated by HPLC) in ripe, unripe samples and total antioxidant activity and LDL oxidation prevention activities of the unripe and ripe samples (100 $\mu\text{g}/\text{ml}$ at 5hrs and 20hrs).

	Total antioxidant activity	LDL oxidation (5h)	LDL oxidation(20h)
Total Phenolic content	1	1	1
Gallic acid	-1	-1	-1
Protocatechin	-1	-1	-1
Chlorogenic acid	1	1	1
Vanillin	-1	-1	-1
Coumaric acid	-1	-1	-1
Sinapic acid	1	1	1
Ferulic acid	1	1	1
Cinnamic acid	1	1	1

CONCLUSION

Since *P. minima* has much medicinal value and it can grow in less cost condition, *Physalis* species has been a plant of interest in horticultural and food industry. Not much research has been carried on its nutraceutical and human health potential. Since the fruits are edible both in ripe and unripe conditions it could be interesting to see which stage would be the best for consumption purposes and beneficial in food formulations. The results indicated that the *P. minima* unripe fruits contained higher amount of phenolics indicating that this could be the reason for its better activity than the ripe fruits. Even though the ripe fruits had good antioxidant potential, their activities were found to be considerably less than those of unripe fruits. Moreover, unripe fruits had a very high foam cell preventing and anti-inflammatory activity. Hence these could be further exploited for nutraceutical or pharmaceutical purposes to combat atherosclerosis.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

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